

DISTRIBUTION OF THE POSTAGE STAMP AS AN INFORMATION PRODUCT IN UKRAINE: REGULATORY SUPPORT

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ABSTRACT

The article provides an author's version of the division of legal documents into groups, depending on the name of the authority that adopted the act. In the analysis of regulatory and legal support, the relationship between the norms established by international and national legal acts is highlighted. It was noted that based on the normative documents of the Universal Postal Union and the World Philatelic Development Association, relevant thematic postal issues are under consideration. These postal issues inform about the national historical and cultural heritage of the state.

Introduction. Philately is widely known as a part of fundamental science. The meaning of Philately for History was formed from its derivative - a postage stamp. The term "postage stamp", as a sign of postage, denoting an element of economic communication between countries, was introduced in 1840 by D. Hill [9, p. 90]. This and other aspects encourage the study of the historical context of the "postage stamp" to investigate the process of its establishment and distribution. As well it is interesting to investigate the life cycle of a postage stamp, the practice of its usage in economics, technology, history and collecting to conclude the level of socio-economic development of the state, the intensity of international postal communications, foreign policy relations, and at the domestic political level - to identify development trends both in the field of stamp-issuing and historical science

in general. This task is becoming increasingly relevant in connection with global digitalization. According to S. Pavlenko, the capabilities of a postage stamp, as a notaphily source, have a complex and multifaceted pictorial and informational potential: "a carrier of historical information, which depicts: emblems, coats of arms, ornaments, portraits, filigree, as well as inscriptions, dates, denomination figures, autographs of officials" [11]. In the history of stamp-issuing and philately, there are few most significant world events for the state, society, and science. R. Bishkevich and his fundamental work "An outline of the history of Ukrainian philately" [4], the work of philatelist-analyst V. Furman "National standard postage stamps of Ukraine" [8], A. Potylchak's work "Philatelic materials as a historical source: information potential, classification and

systematization criteria" [25] and other works have made a significant contribution to the study of the history of Ukrainian stamp-issuing. Aside from that, the scientists study: the history of the origin of postage stamps [13], their varieties and technological purpose [15; 10]; the distribution of postage stamps as a monetary state system of Ukraine [12]; the development of international postal exchanges of written correspondence in Ukraine [16]; collecting as a tool for education and knowledge transfer [30].

The study of these works allows formulating the general assumption that most scientists follow: stamp-issuing is a universal collective activity being of great importance in the development of society and the state. The regulatory documents are another important group for the study. Moreover, these documents can be both a consequence and a reason for the need to study, and modify existing international principles, trends and mechanisms, both in science and in legal systems and practices relating to the monetary system of the state. However, little attention is paid to the establishment of a unified legal framework as a centralized institutional system of stamp-issuing, which is the organizational basis for ensuring the uniformity of the issue and distribution of postal payment marks. In this regard, the article is aimed to establish the level of regulatory and legal security for the process of distribution of a postal stamp as an information product in Ukraine and its compliance with international standards.

Methods. The methodological essence of this issue corresponds to the principles of historicism, objective reflection of reality, and dialectical principles which are applied with the help of chronological, analytical-

logical and comparative methods. According to the sources, there are several approaches to the study of the history of stamp-issuing in the scientific works, it is interpreted as an auxiliary science of history or as the evolution of scientific approaches to the definition of individual narrative and legal sections and aspects in the postal service. As for the state organization of postmarks issued in Ukraine, there are two basic trends: national and international. These trends are based on the unification of rules and standards for the issuing and distribution of postage marks. We propose to divide the history of Ukrainian philately from the standpoint of state regulation into four groups of legal documents, the description of which is presented in the "Results and discussion" section: 1) international legal acts; 2-3) documents of information and legal nature; 4) state standards and certificates. Based on the practical significance of the study, practical recommendations are given both for further scientific research of the issue and for improving the work at the legislative international and domestic levels.

Research results. Postal services are an important part of every country's economic and social sphere. This area is characterized by specific trends and plays a leading role in the formation of the information society [12, p. 5]. A postage stamp is a means of payment for postal services. Its importance for communication between citizens, enterprises, institutions, organizations, and public associations of a particular state and at the international level is undeniable. However, the functional purpose of a postage stamp is not limited to the means of payment for postal services for the forwarding of

written correspondence. In the work "National Standard Postage Stamps of Ukraine" [8], it is said that the postage stamp is also a means of transmitting information that shapes the consciousness of the nation as a whole and individual citizens about historical events and figures, cultural features, scientific and technical achievements, natural conditions, etc. From the very beginning, the postage stamp was considered an original expression of the culture of the respective country due to the unique form of miniature work of art and worldwide coverage. Maria Zofia Libera considers the postage stamp to be the most valuable promoter of cultural heritage [15, p. 223].

Studying the geography of philately, the authors of the study focus on the fact that the last witnesses to the existence of the vanished countries are postage stamps [13]. In addition, postage stamps are a valuable means of communication, and "illustrations on stamps evoke the joy of understanding that can be shared by all people, regardless of worldview" [10]. Potilchak A., a naive scientist, considers postage stamps and postal correspondence as a historical sources because of their main feature - to accumulate, store and reflect various information about the past, to reflect various aspects of human activities in the real historical process [25, p. 82]. The status of a postage stamp - a state mark indicating its face value and the state - obliges to regulate the processes of its issuance, introduction into circulation, organization of distribution, and withdrawal from circulation according to the regulations. Strict compliance with the established regulatory requirements is possible based on a thorough acquaintance with the Ukrainian legal framework of

branding, decrees, resolutions, rules, and procedures adopted by the President of Ukraine, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, central executive bodies, national and industry standards, organizational and administrative documentation. Ukrainian State Enterprise of Postal Services ("Ukrposhta") and their systematic use in current activities. This emphasizes the relevance of the study of regulatory and legal support of technological processes from publication to the withdrawal of the postage stamp, in particular the process of its distribution, including as an information product. The documents that make up the legal framework for the provision of postal services, in particular, the distribution of the postage stamp can be divided into the following groups: international legal acts; laws of Ukraine; by-laws, and national standards for postal services; organizational and administrative documentation of the national operator. The first group of documents - international legal acts - is represented by the regulations and materials of the Congresses of the Universal Postal Union (UPU). Ukraine is a full member of the organization. These documents provide for the implementation of international postal relations, regulation of the issuing postage stamps and the creation of favourable conditions for the development of international cooperation of Ukraine in the world postal system. An important step in confirming the intentions of our state to comply with international standards of postal services was the designation of "Ukrposhta" as a postal operator that fulfils its obligations according to the UPU [21]. The need for such a decision made by the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine is that according to Article 2 of the Universal

Postal Convention, UPU member states after the UPU Congress inform the International Bureau of the name and address of the government body responsible for monitoring communication, as well as the name and address of the operator officially appointed to provide postal services and perform obligations in its territory following the acts of the UPU [29]. Thus, by changing the form of ownership, "Ukrposhta", as a national operator, confirmed the relevant information about itself, assuring UPU and all its members of proper and quality performance of the postal operator in Ukraine and processing of international postal items following international standards. "Ukrposhta" carries out a postal exchange with all 192 UPU member countries following the regulations and acts, while the company carries out the direct postal exchange with 75 countries around the world.

The second and third groups of documents of the legal framework are represented by the Constitution of Ukraine [31]; Decisions of the Constitutional Court of Ukraine [6], Laws of Ukraine: "On postal service" [2], "On the National Archival fund and archival institutions" [3], "On museums and museum business" [1]; by-laws of the President, Government, Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine, namely: "On approval of the Rules for the provision of postal services" [20], "Regulations on postage stamps", [27], "Composition of the Editorial and Artistic Council" [18]. Many of them are complex but include rules of information and legal content. The Constitution of Ukraine guarantees the right of every citizen to freedom of thought and speech, to express their views and

beliefs; the right to freely disseminate information orally and in writing. The right to exchange information, in particular by post, is also enshrined in Article 31. According to this article, every citizen is guaranteed the right to correspondence and the right to secrecy of correspondence and other correspondence [31].

The basic document for the postal service is the Law of Ukraine "On Postal Service" [2]. The law defines the legal, socio-economic and organizational principles of activities in the field of postal services, as well as regulates relations between public authorities and local governments, postal operators and service users. The Law of Ukraine "On Postal Services" defines the basic principles of activities in the field of postal services: protection of users' interests; ensuring the provision of postal services of the established level of quality; accessibility to the postal market; legislative regulation of relations in the field of postal services; ensuring the rights of users to the secrecy of information in the field of postal services; unity of rules, standards and norms in the field of postal services. The law provides general definitions of the services provided by the unified national postal operator. Article 21 states: "[...] Postage stamps (in particular, printed on postal envelopes and postcards) are a means of payment for postal services for the forwarding of written correspondence provided by the national operator [...]" [2]. The national operator has the right to issue postage stamps, stamped envelopes and cards on topics and samples, which are agreed with the Editorial Board, the composition, functions, rights and responsibilities of which are determined by the authorized central executive body in the field of

communications. Since 1992, Ukraine has been the issuer of postage stamps. Every year, since 1997, stamps and stamp blocks have been issued on the common theme of the regional organization of postal administrations of European countries - Post Europe. In 2001 the stamp "Dialogue of Civilizations" was issued, with the same pictures to the all states-members of UPU which took part in the simultaneous issuing of such stamps on World Post Day [14, pp. 166, 200, 203], and which for more than a quarter of a century is a unique fund of postal attribution of the country.

Article 27 of the Law of Ukraine "On Postal Services" defines relations between UPU member states. The activities of the Postal Service of Ukraine are aimed at developing the effective functioning of postal services that promote international cooperation in cultural, social and economic terms. The article regulates international legal cooperation in the field of postal services, which is carried out following the legislation of Ukraine and the relevant international treaties of Ukraine, the binding nature of which is approved by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. It is noted that the National Operator in the manner prescribed by the legislation of Ukraine, supports cooperation with postal operators of other countries, and ensures the implementation of decisions specified by regulations of the Universal Postal Union [2]. The main goal of international cooperation is to facilitate all categories of consumers with the provision of high-quality postal services. International cooperation should be carried out on the appropriate legal basis. The legal basis for Ukraine's cooperation in such international communications organizations as UPU, the Association of European Posts, and the

Regional Commonwealth in the field of communications is the signing by Ukraine of the statutory documents of these organizations. An important part of international activities is participation in international forums, where it is possible not only to obtain information on promising areas of communication, adopted standards and proposals, restrictions and benefits to service providers, but also to influence the management of certain decisions and proposals, implementing the policy of protection of Ukraine's interests in the field of communications. Ukraine's international prestige in the world community determines its membership in the UPU Governing Body, which was obtained at the XXI UPU Congress (Seoul, 1994) [16, p. 21]. Postal services are provided following the Rules for the Provision of Postal Services of March 5, 2009, № 270, approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, and must meet the established quality standards [20]. The operator's responsibilities include providing consumers with high-quality services in the field of postal services, physical delivery of postal items, and financial and other publicly available services. Among the wide variety of services (more than 50 types), the object of our study is universal services. This is a set of mandatory public postal services of the established level of quality, which are provided to all users throughout Ukraine at tariffs regulated by the state. In addition, the provision of universal postal services is one of the objectives of the Universal Postal Convention (UPC). The list of universal services includes five ones, which are related to the sending of normal and registered mail: cards, letters, parcels, parcels without declared value, and sec

grams (for visually impaired consumers, the written message is written se graphically in Braille). According to the main provisions of the UPC, such services are franked with state postage stamps.

The Ministry of Transport and Communications approved the Regulations on Postage Signs according to Order No. 248 of June 24, 2010, registered with the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine on July 26, 2010, No. 553/17848. This Regulation was adopted to bring the regulations applicable to the provision of postal services according to the acts of the UPU, the Law of Ukraine "On Postal Services" (Article 15) and the Rules for the provision of postal services, approved by the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 05.03.2009 for № 270 III [32]. The initial document was the "Regulations on Postage Stamps, Blocks, Stamped Envelopes and Cards" developed in 1996 (№762 / 1787 of 30.12.1996). Over fourteen years, the conditions of the regulation have undergone significant changes. Thus, it was necessary to improve the regulations taking into account the relevant conditions under the acts of the UPU (revised in 2004 № 725/9324). The main difference is that, following Article 8 of the Universal Postal Convention (in previous conventions, Article 6), which was revised at the UPU Congress in Bucharest (2004), the postage stamp has acquired a new meaning and can be defined and consolidated at the level of the national legislation. This document is important and indispensable in the stamp-issuing of the state. This Regulation determines the procedure for issuing, putting into circulation and withdrawing from circulation, and organization of distribution for postage stamps, which include postage stamps, blocks, stamped

envelopes and cards. This Regulation applies to the national postal operator, the functions of which are entrusted to "Ukrposhta" by the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on January 10, 2002. The Regulation uses twelve terms that reveal the essence of the concepts of a postage stamp (artistic, standard), block, small sheet, postcard and envelope (marked, artistic), face value, and philatelic products, which is important not only for domestic professionals in communications and collectors but also for the world community. Thus, Article 3 defines: "Postage stamp - a state mark made in the manner prescribed by law, indicating the face value and the state; is a means of payment for postal services provided by national operators" [27]. Article 4 states that postage stamps are a manifestation of the sovereignty of the state, and as a personification of sovereignty contains the name of the country issuing the stamp (in Latin letters); State Emblem of Ukraine; face value. By these actions, "Ukrposhta", as an issuer of postage stamps, fulfils the provisions specified in the Convention and the General Regulations of the UPU and the current Additional Protocol to the UPU Statute (Istanbul, 2016) [17]. Postage stamp, as a state symbol and personification of state sovereignty is designed to encourage interest in Ukraine and its achievements is an advertising and propaganda tool and a means of celebrating significant events in the history of Ukraine and promoting its cultural heritage.

The fourth group of documents that form the regulatory and legal support for the implementation of technological processes from publication to the withdrawal of the postage stamp, in particular the process of

its distribution, are national and industry standards of Ukraine, in particular: DSTU 3875-99 [23]; DSTU 3876-99 [24]; GSTU 45.027-2003 [27]. Standardization of the issuing of postage stamps, blocks, cards, and envelopes is necessary to comply with the relevant legislation of Ukraine, the provisions for multiple uses of relevant products, their functional purpose, and removing barriers to the sale of products and services. The abovementioned DSTU regulates printing, technological and technical characteristics for printing stamps, blocks, cards, and envelopes, namely: size, format, perforation (for stamps), paper density, watermarks on paper (filigree), paper type, printing type, manufacturing method, fluorescent and colour inks. A special role in the formation of the studied regulatory and legal support is played by the organizational and administrative documentation of the national operator JSC "Ukrposhta". It is represented by regulations, rules, resolutions, orders and directives, work plans of normative significance: Regulations for Internal Written Correspondence [28], Thematic Plan for Issuance of Art Postage Stamps and Blocks, Thematic Plan for Issuance of Envelopes, Thematic Plan for Special Repayments, Procedure for Distribution of Ukrposhta Postage Stamps payment and philatelic products by subscription [33].

According to the requirements of the World Association of Philately (hereinafter - WADP) and UPU "Ukrposhta", as the national operator of Ukraine, notifies the International Bureau of UPU of each new issue of postage stamps to inform other authorized bodies and to provide issue number in the stamp numbering system (WNS WADP). The Editorial and Artistic

Council for the Issuance of Postage Stamps is a coordinating expert-advisory body at the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine. The Council is guided by the Constitution of Ukraine, laws of Ukraine, resolutions of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, acts of the President and the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, as well as the Regulations approved by the State Communications Committee, 2002 [26]. Among the basic tasks assigned to the council, the main ones are: 1. Coordination of work on the preparation of topics (considers annual thematic plans for the issuance of postage stamps; considers appeals and proposals received from the executive authorities, enterprises, institutions, associations and other collective organizations for the issuance of postage stamps; considers projects and sketches of drawings from which it is planned to make postage stamps, and redemption stamps; provides and supports proposals for the issuance of postage stamps dedicated to historical events, prominent figures of culture, science and technology, sports, military and other events both in Ukraine and internationally, as well as depicting monuments of architecture, nature, plant and wildlife); 2. Improvement of the quality and decoration of materials (approves the originals of postage stamps prepared for submission to production; provides specific proposals for improving the design of drawings, sketches and printing reproduction of postage stamps; recommends some highly artistic works for exposition at domestic and international exhibitions; studies the mechanism of prevention and detection of counterfeit postage stamps; provides proposals to improve the production of postage stamps in Ukraine and abroad). The editorial and

artistic board is determined and approved by the authorized central executive body in the field of communications. The current board was approved by the order of March 31, 2009, of the Ministry of Transport and Communications of Ukraine. The editorial and artistic board includes specialists in the field of communications and publishers of the "Ukraine" printing plant, representatives of the Board of the Association of Philatelists of Ukraine, the National Union of Artists of Ukraine and the Council of the Ukrainian Heraldic Society, teachers of the Kyiv Academy of Arts [18]. Postage stamps are issued by the national operator according to annual thematic plans, which are agreed with the editorial and artistic board. The composition, functions, rights and responsibilities of the editorial and artistic board following Article 21 of the Law of Ukraine "On Postal Services" are determined by the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine.

The subject of postage stamps reflects: plots of the state system of Ukraine; historical past of Ukraine; cultural heritage of the Ukrainian people; achievements in the fields of the national economy; special events of domestic and international life; prominent personalities of Ukraine who form a positive image of the state. The subject of issuing postage stamps is determined by the requirements of the Decree issued by the President of Ukraine of 02.12.95 № 1116 [22] and the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 13.08.2003 № 1249 "On approval of Procedure for preparation and submission to the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine for acceptance of proposals for the celebration of memorable dates and anniversaries" [19]. The thematic plan for issuing postage

stamps, blocks, stamped envelopes and cards for the next year is formed by the national operator based on orders of its branches (regional directorates), as well as proposals of enterprises, institutions, organizations, NGOs, Philatelic Association of Ukraine, other associations, political and public figures of science and culture, received not later than twelve months before the beginning of the year preceding the planned one. Each proposal is confirmed by the relevant historical references, which ensures the authenticity of the historical event, and the activities of prominent personalities. Under the terms of the current Article 13, the national operator reserves the right to determine the number of subjects and the circulation of postage stamps but taking into account the needs of the users of postal services. After approval of the thematic plan, the national operator, following Article 17 of the Regulations, organizes appropriate actions for the development of plots (sketches, original future images, etc.) with the involvement of specialists in culture, art and other activities in this area. Thus, the thematic plan for the issue of artistic postage stamps and blocks for 2022 provides for the issuing of twelve topics (29 stories) of postage stamps. The thematic plan for the issue of artistic envelopes with original stamps for 2022 provides for issues in the thematic area: outstanding personalities; modernity; art and architecture; mail and philately; children's themes. By the way, 9 topics are planned, and this is up to 30 subjects, two of them are new ones: religion; education and science. Activities on the distribution of postage stamps are determined by the exclusive right of the national operator, regulated by the Law of Ukraine "On Postal

Services" (Article 15) [2], the Decision of the Constitutional Court of Ukraine of 28.05.2003 №10-rp/2003 [6], Regulations on Postage Stamps [27] and Instructions on the Procedure for Forming Circulations, Ordering, Supplying, Accounting and Storing Postage Stamps at the Ukrainian State Postal Enterprise "Ukrposhta", approved by the order of USPE "Ukrposhta" on 10.09.2009 № 771 and normative document developed and approved by USEPS "Ukrposhta", which regulates the peculiarities of the activity of the national postal operator (Procedure for the organization of distribution of postage stamps by the Ukrainian State Enterprise of Postal Services "Ukrposhta" [32].

The current procedure determines the procedure for distribution of postage stamps through the network of postal facilities of JSC "Ukrposhta", where services are provided to users, as well as based on concluded agreements according to the requirements of the Civil and Commercial Codes of Ukraine, taking into account the peculiarities defined by the current legislation in the field of public procurement. The purpose of this document is to fully meet the needs of service users, without limiting their ability to purchase stamps, stamped envelopes and cards. To preserve the national heritage, the national operator has organized an archive of postage stamps. Postage stamps issued by the authorized bodies of the UPU member states and received by the Communications Administration of Ukraine through the UPU International Bureau in the order of exchange are entered into the archive. Museum and reserve funds have also been formed and are constantly updated. The museum fund provides storage of postage

stamps and other philatelic products of historical significance for Ukraine. Postage stamps in the reserve fund are formed for further implementation, in particular through exhibitions and auctions. Accounting, storage and exhibiting of postage stamps in the funds are provided following the requirements of the Laws of Ukraine "On the National Archival Fund and archival institutions" [3] and "On museums and museum business" [1]. In addition to regulating the issuance and distribution of postage stamps, the Law of Ukraine "On the National Archival Fund and archival institutions" regulates the procedure for forming funds by documents of the cultural heritage of Ukraine. Thus, to fulfil the second part of Article 5 of this law, the state takes measures to replenish the National Archival Fund with documents of the cultural heritage of Ukraine which are located abroad and documents of foreign origin related to the history of Ukraine [3]. Such documents include postage stamps of the Ukrainian People's Republic and the Western Ukrainian People's Republic, which are found among the documents of private correspondence of public and cultural persons, writers, actors, and artists, as well as in their collections of stamps and postcards. R. Byshkevych researched the history of stamp publishing in the Ukrainian and Western Ukrainian People's Republics. He identified aspects of the philatelic movement in the Ukrainian lands from its establishment in the late nineteenth century until 1939, as well as its origin and development outside the Ukrainian lands [4]. The distribution of postage stamps and philatelic products by "Ukrposhta" is regulated by a document of the appropriate name and approved by the order of the Director-General dated

20.10.2014 № 756, and previous orders accordingly invalidated [33]. The season ticket can be owned by an individual who collects or is going to start collecting Ukrainian philatelic products. The season ticket holder is guaranteed to receive postage stamps and other philatelic products issued during the year. Therefore, "Ukrposhta" undertakes to provide the relevant consumer with a complete set of products, which is thirty-one items.

The purpose of the Procedure is to regulate relations on the distribution of postage stamps and philatelic products by subscription, create appropriate conditions to meet consumer needs, support the development of the philatelic movement in Ukraine and encourage membership in the Association of Philatelists of Ukraine (APU) to promote and preserve historical memory using postage stamps. To establish effective cooperation between key players and stakeholders in the field of philately based on UPU recommendations and relevant global trends in this field in 2013 "Ukrposhta" and APU developed and approved the Concept of Philately in Ukraine [5]. The tasks are as follows: state support in this direction; organization of cooperation in the field of propaganda and popularization of philately with state institutions; development of the philatelic market in Ukraine (increase in the number of adult collectors and consumers of Ukrainian philatelic products); development of youth philately; increasing the prestige of Ukrainian issues of postage stamps in the international philatelic sector among the member countries of the Universal Postal Union. The development of collecting and youth philately is also rapidly developing. Studying the art of collecting, Renata Tańczuk (Doctor of

Philosophy, Professor, Institute of Cultural Studies, University of Wrocław) reveals the concept of collecting: "Collecting is an activity that gives value. Material objects, which in our tradition we often see as a heavy burden, acquire value in the collection" [30, p. 14].

To educate a new generation of collectors, a curriculum for extracurricular education in the humanitarian field "Young Philatelists" was developed. The program was approved by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine in 2014 to establish philatelic clubs in schools and out-of-school institutions [7]. There are issues of children's art postage stamps dedicated to other events, at low denominations. This series of issues "The world through the eyes of children" was developed, in which the authors of the stamps are children, and the plotline is children's drawings [14, p. 195]. They organize special celebrations with the participation of the youth audience during the introduction of postage stamps on the subject; publish children's literature on philatelic topics; carry out excursions for children to the museums of post offices and exposition and shopping centres "Philately". Exhibitions and integrated point-of-sale marketing communications are effective means of synthetic communications to communicate with consumers and achieve marketing goals. The annual holding of national philatelic exhibitions, as well as participation in international ones, is an active method of positioning and promoting domestic philatelic products. The process of building effective marketing communications is carried out through the media, such as advertising, sales promotion and public relations.

To inform the general public about the introduction into circulation and withdrawal of postage stamps, and events in the world of collecting, the national operator normally submits relevant messages in periodicals: "Postal Bulletin" (newspaper) and "Philately of Ukraine" (journal), on the corporate website "Ukrposhta" and other advertising and information platforms.

Among the numerous image functions, corporate publishing houses implement the following: informing consumers, partners and staff about the state of affairs at the enterprise, actions and plans of management, and the situation in the domestic and international markets of postal services; informing about new services and issues of postal products of the enterprise, promoting cooperation between "Ukrposhta" and partners. Collectors-researchers present their ideas in the journals, they publish essays about famous philatelists, artists-authors of stamps, materials about stamps and collections, and various information on philately issues are highlighted. Parts of catalogues of domestic and foreign reproductions of stamps, envelopes, and stamps of special redemptions are

regularly submitted. The materials of these publishing houses provide an opportunity to learn more about the history and development of philately in Ukraine and other countries, with many theoretical and practical issues in collecting philatelic materials. Implementation of the concept of philately development will contribute to expanding the number of fans and collectors of domestic philatelic products; strengthening the authority of the state and popularizing historical heritage; increasing the volume of sales of postage stamps and philatelic products.

Conclusions. The Ukrainian legal framework for branding regulates the main technological processes, including compliance with international standards. The result is a postage stamp, which has to contain design elements as a trademark, which is considered an attribute of the sovereignty of the issuing state. This information, spreading beyond Ukraine, is useful for strengthening the image of our country in the international area as an independent and sovereign one. The information presented on the post stamps also contributes to the establishment of Ukraine's international prestige as a philatelic state.

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